

Recommendations to implement wild boar carcass detection and dating in different environments

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Abstract

The prompt and efficient detection and disposal of wild boar carcasses is crucial in minimising the transmission of African Swine Fever (ASF). Additionally, accurately and quickly determining the *post-mortem* interval (PMI) of carcasses provides valuable information on the timing of ASF introduction, or on confirming disease elimination in the area. ENETWILD consortium already reviewed methods for locating and dating wild boar carcasses in various scenarios. However, these activities are not generally implemented systematically (due to the absence of protocols or detailed guidance), and information on field surveys is often neither reported nor made available to the public. The aim of this report is to highlight the key factors to consider when planning wild boar carcass search and dating methods in different scenarios. Our goal is to provide general guidance to facilitate the harmonised collection of the minimum necessary data during field activities related to carcass search and dating.

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Key words: ASF management, surveillance, wild boar carcass search, forensic dating, early detection, freedom of disease, recommendations

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Summary

Background: Efficient detection, rapid removal and safe disposal of wild boar carcasses are crucial to minimising the transmission of African swine fever (ASF), with the term 'carcass' encompassing not only the complete body, but also individual parts (such as bones), depending on the decomposition stage. Additionally, accurately and quickly determining the *post-mortem* interval (PMI) of carcasses provides valuable information on the timing of ASF introduction or eventual disease elimination in the area. A previous report by the ENETWILD consortium reviewed methods for locating and dating wild boar carcasses in various scenarios (ENETWILD Consortium, 2025). This review revealed a lack of systematic and harmonised approaches within European countries to carcass search and dating (due to the absence of protocols or detailed guidance), and that information such as protocols, method applications and field survey results are often not reported or are kept as internal documents. This report aims to provide recommendations for the implementation of wild boar carcass detection and dating in different environments.

Methods: Information collected from literature and grey sources (presented in a separate report) outlines the key elements determining the applicability and performance of different methods for searching for and dating wild boar carcasses. It also includes a descriptive analysis of the relative advantages and disadvantages of the methods, approaches and strategies employed in different scenarios based on peer-reviewed literature but also on grey sources and interviews to key stakeholders involved in carcass search and dating activities. This foundational dataset will provide the basis for developing guidelines and adaptable data formats designed to standardise and harmonise the monitoring of these activities. The structure is presented as follows:

- The main limitations and factors determining the applicability and performance of different wild boar carcass search and dating methods in different scenarios are presented and discussed, along with the best-known and recommended options in every case. This is summarised in comparative tables reporting relative advantages and disadvantages.
- The main considerations for designing and implementing activities involving the search for and dating of wild boar carcasses.
- Flexible, indicative template forms for collecting essential data during field activities involving carcass searches and dating. These forms are designed to be adaptable across a wide range of scenarios, facilitating the standardisation of data collection for further analysis, as well as the improvement of search and dating strategies.

Guidance on wild boar carcass search:

The effective planning of field operations for wild boar carcass search is generally context dependent but should involve several key steps:

1. BEFORE: planning the search

Define objectives and scope

- Primary objective: detect and remove ASF-infected carcasses to prevent disease spread.
- Clearly define the search area: include both infected zones and surrounding areas (focal outbreaks or large fronts).
- Align objectives with available resources, collaborative frameworks, and feasible methodologies.

Build the team and the collaboration framework

- Define roles and responsibilities for all team members.

- Engage relevant stakeholders: veterinary services, forestry departments, hunters, local communities.
- Establish clear communication channels and coordination mechanisms.
- Plan training and simulation exercises to improve readiness and coordination.

Prepare resources and train the team

- Train all personnel on:
 - ASF epidemiology and transmission
 - Carcass detection and identification
 - Biosecurity protocols and PPE use
 - Safe carcass handling and sampling
 - Data collection and reporting
 - Use of GPS and navigation tools
- Prepare and distribute equipment:
 - GPS devices, PPE, disinfectants, communication tools
 - Documentation tools: notebooks, pens, cameras, mobile devices
 - Maps, signalling tape, data recording forms/apps

Design the search strategy

- Select search patterns and methods (grid search, transects, detection dogs, drones).
- Use habitat-based strategies for targeted searches and grid-based strategies for systematic coverage; often combine both.
- Identify hotspots through local knowledge (hunters, foresters, farmers).
- Plan the search area coverage:
 - Start at the outbreak centre and search outward.
 - Include car patrols in risky zones.
 - Adjust the area as new cases emerge.
- Plan search frequency and timing, considering risk levels and seasonal/environmental factors

2. DURING: coordinate and carry out the search

Coordinate the search operations

- Ensure all teams follow the planned strategy and communication protocols.
- Monitor biosecurity compliance to prevent further disease spread.
- Adapt activities dynamically as new findings emerge.

Carry out the carcass search

- Execute the planned search methods (visual search, detection dogs, drones, beaters, etc.).
- Document all findings:
 - GPS coordinates
 - Carcass decomposition stage
 - Environmental context
- Follow safe carcass handling and biosecurity procedures.

3. AFTER: Communicate and build upon

Manage and report data

- Record data accurately and consistently using standardized forms/apps.

- Ensure data integrity and secure storage.
- Share results through coordinated reporting systems for surveillance and response planning.

Review and improve the process

- Regularly review search protocols based on field experience and scientific updates.
- Share search results to support adaptive management and collaborative learning.
- Use findings to improve future search strategies and coordination.

Proposed tools for data collection

Two standard forms are recommended to facilitate data collection:

1. **Search Event Form:** documenting methods, area covered, and effort applied.
2. **Carcass Record Form:** describing each carcass found.

Both forms can be integrated into mobile apps to streamline data entry and sharing.

Guidance on wild boar carcass dating:

The stages of decomposition of a wild boar carcass can vary significantly due to environmental factors such as temperature, humidity, sunlight exposure and the activity of both vertebrate and invertebrate scavengers. To improve accuracy, we recommend implementing a standardised method of recording the decomposition status alongside the date of discovery. This would minimise discrepancies in estimating infection dating, particularly in high-risk zones where systematic carcass searches are conducted rather than relying on opportunistic findings. One practical solution would be to classify carcasses into five distinct decomposition categories, which should be included in standardised data collection forms. This approach would enhance the reliability of ASF surveillance and outbreak analyses.

First, we summarised the main advantages and disadvantages of the different methods for dating wild boar carcasses, as well as their applicability. Next, we present a general guidance plan, including a field protocol form, for dating wild boar carcasses in the context of ASF control. The aim is to accurately determine the *post-mortem* interval (PMI) of wild boar carcasses to improve ASF surveillance. The plan below ensures systematic data collection for further carcass dating, which supports ASF monitoring and helps to estimate infection timelines.

1. Preparation before fieldwork

Equipment needed (dependent on applied technique):

- PPE, including disposable gloves and boot covers.
- Sampling kit: swabs, scalpel, forceps, sample bags, containers, labels and a cooler with ice.
- Documentation tools:
 - GPS device
 - Camera
 - Datasheet
 - Waterproof pen
 - Electronic devices
- Carcass assessment tools: decomposition scoring sheet and measuring tape.
- Disinfection supplies: ASF-approved disinfectants
- Safety considerations: follow biosecurity protocols to prevent the spread of ASF (disinfect equipment and avoid cross-contamination).
- Record GPS coordinates and mark the carcass location for follow-up.
- Measures for personal protection and equipment required during ground-based carcass searches and recovery operations. Considerations include whether to carry firearms to euthanise live diseased wild boar if encountered, or for the teams' own safety.

2. Carcass discovery and initial assessment.

- Step 1: Locate and document. Record:
 - GPS coordinates
 - Date and time of discovery
 - Age class: age determination should be based on teeth eruption for accuracy
 - Habitat type (forest, field, water proximity)
 - Habitat at the location of the carcass
 - Weather conditions (temperature, humidity, recent rainfall)
- Step 2: Photograph the carcasses:
 - Take multiple angles (surrounding of the carcass, whole body, head, limbs, visible lesions, insects present on the body, especially mouth and anus, teeth – primarily incisors, if possible, also cheek teeth, i.e. premolars and molars)
 - Include a scale (e.g., ruler or glove for size reference)

3. *Post-Mortem* decomposition assessment

A standardised decomposition scoring system is presented for indicative purposes only, including some indications specific to a moderate climate and additional indicators. It should be noted that the estimated PMI requires regionally performed experimental studies over different seasons, with a sufficient variety of carcasses deployed under natural conditions.

4. Collect information on environmental factors affecting decomposition (more relevant for experimental studies).

- Temperature: Use a thermometer to record ambient temperature
- Humidity and rainfall: Accelerates decomposition
- Sun exposure: Direct sunlight accelerates decay compared to shaded areas
- Insects' activity

5. Carcass disposal.

- As required by national and local regulations

Finally, we present a structured field data collection form for estimating PMI in wild boar carcasses. This form can easily be incorporated into portable devices as an app, ensuring systematic data collection for PMI estimation in wild boar carcasses while accounting for environmental factors, decomposition stages and key indicators.

1. Introduction

In areas where African swine fever (ASF) is prevalent, the presence of infected wild boar carcasses enables the ASF virus to persist, even when the wild boar population has been significantly reduced. Therefore, the efficient detection, removal and disposal of these carcasses is crucial to minimise ASF transmission. Additionally, accurately and quickly determining the *post-mortem* interval (PMI) of carcasses provides valuable information on the timing of ASF introduction. This aids disease control strategies and surveillance, such as defining restriction zones and later confirming that the area is free of disease.

A separate report by the ENETWILD consortium (ENETWILD Consortium, 2025) reviewed various methods for locating and dating wild boar carcasses in different scenarios, considering the factors affecting their effectiveness and practical application. However, the performance of these methods was rarely quantified, and the approaches varied widely, making comparisons difficult. While experimental studies may compare the number of carcasses found to those hidden, in real scenarios the number of carcasses is unknown. Sometimes, estimates can be made based on modelling. Performance could also be estimated relative to the wild boar population; however, these estimations are typically unreliable, and the local impact of mortality depends on the epidemic phase.

1.1 Review of methods for locating and dating wild boar carcasses under different scenarios

The main conclusions regarding wild boar carcass search were:

- Although the timely removal of wild boar carcasses following the detection of initial cases (and in subsequent phases) is of critical importance, protocols and guidance for their detection are often notably lacking.
- This scarcity of publicly available protocols and guidance on wild boar carcass search indicates the need for publishing and transferring what is already known locally based on experience, both concerning the large front of disease in Europe and focal outbreaks of ASF.
- Relevant research steps, mainly in central Europe, have experimentally been done in relation to wild boar carcass search and carcass dating (Rietz *et al.* 2023; Müller *et al.* 2024; Probst *et al.* 2020). Further testing and adapting these studies over different biogeographical and epidemiological scenarios in Europe is needed to evaluate their efficiency (carcass search) as well as precision (carcass dating).
- In Europe, the majority of specific literature originated from few ASF affected countries. Most national veterinary administrations often answered that no systematic protocol on wild boar carcass search exists. We advocate for agreeing on and incorporating detailed guidance on wild boar carcass search as part of the plans for wild boar monitoring and population control requested by the Commission to Countries in the frame of the fight against ASF.
- Priority criteria used in the surveyed literature to select areas for wild boar carcass search are mainly related to increased risk of finding dead wild boar, and the estimated ASF risk. The optimal approach may involve integrating different strategies to maximize effectiveness. Habitat-based strategies would be more efficient in targeted areas with known wild boar activity and grid-based strategies provide comprehensive coverage and are useful in areas with less known habitat data. The features usually considered for habitat-based strategy include presence of forest types as primary, and then, proximity to water sources, terrain type, and areas with minimal human disturbance.
- One important handicap to build strategies of carcass search on known experiences is that, in addition to the scarcity of data, the performance of wild boar search of different methods has hardly ever been quantified, and worse, the ways and metrics used were not always

comparable. By nature, the number of carcasses found relative to hidden cases is unknown. Another relevant handicap is the scarcity of comparisons of methods (results, efforts and costs, potential complementarity), and particularly, fair comparisons under similar circumstances.

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- An essential part that requires guidance is about the efforts required and the availability of resources to be deployed over time. The parameters provided here offer some guidance to determine human effort and material resources.
- The main factors reported in the literature that may determine the applicability and performance of different protocols for wild boar carcass search are of different nature, and their relevance depends on the local scenario and applied methods, even a given factor may diminish or increase efficacy under different circumstances. The main factors included knowledge of wild boar ecology, economic compensation, use of trained dogs, coordination of administrations, weather conditions and season, visibility of carcasses, and the use of complementary methods.
- Surveillance and searching techniques, such as active ground searching by humans or aerial surveillance, have varying efficacy. While this review identified four main methods for active detection of wild boar carcasses, an integrated approach could enhance the efficiency and coverage of such surveillance efforts, especially in areas that are difficult to access:
 - o Ground surveys teams may work in conjunction with other surveillance tools, such as drones equipped with thermal imaging cameras and carcass detection dogs.
 - o Patrolling by car over known/possible hotspots for wild boar activity or death beds (risk-based surveillance) might complement more systematic search by teams of beaters, drones, and dogs, particularly for initial preliminary estimation of the infected area where more systematic search activities can be developed thereafter. Some habitats in Europe (e.g., forest areas), however, are not accessible for car patrols, while it may work on other regions (e.g., Mediterranean and open areas, Gortazar *et al.* 2002)
 - o The search for carcasses by dog handlers with specially trained dogs is an effective tool for carcass detection, even in close vegetation environments and for small carcasses. Well-trained dogs are probably the most portable and versatile tools in use today for odour.
- Further integration and generalization of use of drone technology into wildlife surveillance is still developing. Drones equipped with thermal imaging cameras have been deployed to monitor wild boar populations, enhancing surveillance and containment efforts in difficult-to-access areas, with use for rapid, efficient, and safe detection of wild boar carcasses.

- The experimental areas requiring further development to gather applied reliable information to have elements of decision under different circumstances and contexts are:
 - o Comparative search experiments need to compare the effectiveness of different methods. Any trial must be done in a way that results can be comparable among zones, using similar (or exchangeable) metrics.
 - o To quantify the probability of detecting a wild boar carcass within a given area. This involves placing known carcasses in the field and conducting repeated searches to determine the detection rate.
 - o Performance testing of trained dogs (and dog handlers) in different environments in order to evaluate how environmental conditions affect canine detection efficiency, and at different decomposition stages.
 - o Technology integration requires addressing specifically drone technology, to compare drone-based searches with ground searches and automatizing wild boar detection.

And the main conclusions for wild boar carcass dating were:

- Determining PMI in wild boar is exceptionally difficult, presenting a great challenge. Beyond some experimental studies (i.e., known PMI), there are not adapted validated protocols and/or detailed guidance on wild boar carcass dating for application of real cases. Whereas known experiences can be adapted from Central Europe to other areas, regional studies with similar methodology are still required (Müller *et al.* 2024).
- The recent development of methods, such as metabolomics-based approaches, seem promising but require further development and appropriate facilities and expertise for rapid assessment (Zacometti *et al.* 2025).
- Estimated PMI by "classical" forensic techniques presented wide ranges of estimations based on the experimental studies, with increasing uncertainty, as time elapsed since death.
- Decomposition stages based mostly on macroscopic evidence cannot be universally associated with specific PMI, which depends on the specific context and conditions. Models or automatic algorithms to estimate the PMI for wild boar due to the complexity of the factors involved are only precise regionally.
- Season as well as habitat and determinants of microhabitat conditions were the most frequent factors considered to have an impact on PMI as well as body size (or age as a proxy), insect activity and scavengers.
- The development and validation of new methods based on understanding metabolomics changes that occur post-mortem are promising, as well as its combination of different approaches.

In conclusion, the main considerations that need to be accounted for when determining the post-mortem interval (PMI) in wild boar across Europe are: (i) extreme environmental variability, meaning extrapolating data from studies in different areas/bioregions is unreliable; (ii) aspects related to specific wild boar decomposition processes; (iii) extrapolating data from domestic pig or human forensic studies is equally unreliable; (iv) the unpredictable scavenger and insect activity characteristic of a given area/bioregion; and (v) the fact that accessing and analysing wild boar carcasses in remote locations often requires work to be done in the field without delay (e. g. entomological analysis) without lab support.

To determine the PMI in wild boar, large-scale experiments must be conducted in various environmental settings and conditions to build a comprehensive understanding of PMI across Europe. This includes decomposition studies and controlled environmental studies. This will also

provide forensic pathologists and ecologists dealing with wild boar carcasses with the necessary baseline data.

The findings described in the previous report have served as a basis for the guidance provided in this second report on the use of carcass detection and dating systems for ASF surveillance and management.

1.2 Background and Terms of Reference

The contract, entitled 'Wildlife and One Health: Wildlife Ecology, Health Surveillance and Interaction with Livestock, Human Populations and the Environment' (framework contract number OC/EFSA/BIOHAW/2022/01), was awarded to the University of Turin by EFSA. We refer to this framework contract as the ENETWILD project. Specific objective 2 (SO2) of the framework contract relates to 'Wildlife ecology, health surveillance and interaction with livestock, the human population and the environment'.

WP 6 (ad-hoc scientific advice) of specific contract 2 indicates as terms of reference:

6.A) To provide a review of different methods to find wild boar carcasses in different countries, and the methods to date those carcasses, based on literature and field experience. This is addressed in the previous report.

6.B) To propose protocols of use for each carcass detection system and carcass dating in different environments, how to adjust the effort depending on factors such as prevalence/seasons/etc. This is addressed in the present report.

Scope of the report

The report aims to provide recommendations to implement wild boar carcass detection and carcass dating in different environments and prevalent factors (ToR 6.B).

2. Methods and general descriptors

We conducted a scoping review of indexed (peer-reviewed) scientific literature and grey literature, including national publications not written in English. We also interviewed administrations and wildlife networks of professionals across Europe. The results of these interviews are presented in a separate report (*ENETWILD Consortium et al., 2025*). The systematic literature review first involved creating search strings and defining inclusion and exclusion criteria. These were then applied to articles screened by topic, title and abstract. The selected articles were then screened in full for further refinement. We also performed snowballing by following citations from included papers to find additional ones. Additionally, national veterinary and wildlife authorities were interviewed and asked for grey literature and protocols on the two issues in question that were not available in the indexed literature. International networks of wildlife veterinarians were interviewed regarding carcass dating. Data extracted from the selected papers and interviews was entered into a database to describe and compare different approaches and list the main factors to consider when defining the best possible methods and practical strategies for different scenarios.

- Regarding the search for wild boar carcasses, a total of 95 documents and/or interviews/questionnaires were ultimately collected that potentially included relevant information on carcass search methods and protocols, their characterisation, and the factors that may affect the findability of such carcasses. Sixty of the 95 documents passed the inclusion filter and provided a description of the main methods used to search for wild boar carcasses: 1) Prospective patrols in areas favourable for the presence of dead wild boar, 2) Systematic combing of an area, 3) Dog detection, and 4) Use of drones. Most of the items were indexed literature ($n = 29$) or interviews ($n = 22$), while grey literature (usually in the form of blogs, technical reports and unpublished presentations) and questionnaires were less well represented. As expected, the majority of items originated from ASF-affected European countries, namely Germany, Italy and Poland. Relevant information was also collected from abroad, albeit to a lesser extent, specifically from South Korea and other South-East Asian countries. These documents mostly referred to ASF-infected areas or areas within 10 km of the infected areas, and to a lesser extent, ASF-free areas. In terms of spatial considerations, we found a similar number of items concerning focal outbreaks and large areas affected by ASF.
- Concerning wild boar carcass dating, a total of 48 documents were collected, including 43 research papers. Eleven out of these were selected for further evaluation of methods on carcass statistics because they referred to wild boar and/or they had developed carcass dating methods later adopted for wild boar. However, all references were screened in detail, and data were included in our proposed data form since they could provide relevant information directly transferable to the evaluation of carcass dating methods in wild boar. For example, these factors may be relevant to other species (wildlife, pigs, humans) or they might be included into epidemiological models (e.g., several reports by EFSA). Three out of them were developed in ASF infected areas, and the geographical distribution was mainly in Europe, particularly in regions that were classified as Atlantic, Continental, and Alpine (mainly central Europe), but similar comparable studies originating from other temperate areas were placed in South Korea ($n=4$). Four out of 11 references referring to wild boar were classified as experimental, which means that wild boar carcasses were experimentally deployed to evaluate the decay process, and PMI was known. On the other hand, in 7 cases the observations originated from field observations, and the exact PMI was unknown. Two out of the 11 references were original, i.e., they developed their own methodology to determine PMI in wild boar carcasses. The remaining 15 applied or adapted methodology already described, using human or animal models. Most frequently, the described methodological

approaches were based on the following original sources: Megyesi *et al.* (2005) (only or in combination with other references) in four cases, followed by Goff (2009), Laehroven (1996), Parsons (2009), and Keough *et al.* (2009). Probst *et al.* (2020) was adopted by several studies, which in turn relied on Megyesi *et al.* 2005 (adapted).

The information collected from literature and grey sources (presented in a separate report) included the main factors determining the applicability and performance of different wild boar carcass search and dating methods. A comprehensive analysis of the relative advantages and disadvantages of methods, approaches and strategies in different scenarios formed the basis for the development of guidance and flexible data forms to further harmonise the monitoring of these activities. This is presented in the following sections: 3 and 4 for wild boar carcass search and dating, respectively).

- The main limitations/factors determining the applicability and performance of different carcass search and dating methods over different scenarios: we present and discuss best known and recommended options in every case. This is summarized in comparative tables on relative advantages and disadvantages.
- The main considerations to design and implement wild boar carcass search and dating activities
- Flexible, indicative template forms for minimum data collection during field activities on carcass search and dating and proposed, with the aim of being useful over a large range of scenarios and to harmonize collected data for further evaluation and improvement of strategies.

3. Guidance on wild boar carcass search

Our aim is to summarise the current knowledge on carcass detection systems and carcass dating in different environments, taking into account the main factors. However, based on the literature presented in a separate report (*ENETWILD Consortium et al., 2025*), it is possible to partially determine the efforts applied. The scarcity of detailed information and the use of different metrics prevented comparisons between methods, strategies, areas and epidemiological scenarios. The real efficacy in terms of the proportion of carcasses found could only be determined through experimental trials. Nevertheless, the presented strategies can be adapted for Central and Southern Europe to facilitate the search for infected carcasses according to local conditions. Field trials are needed to test the efficiency and precision of different methods for carcass search and dating, respectively, and to assess their adoption in different scenarios, following harmonised protocols. Relevant research has recently been conducted in Central Europe (e.g. Rietz *et al., 2023*). These studies require further testing and adoption in different European environments.

The persistence of the ASF virus in the environment (from weeks to months, depending on environmental conditions) necessitates effective strategies for locating and removing these sources of infection, particularly in wild boar carcasses. Having a detailed plan that describes the main procedures for searching for wild boar carcasses is crucial for several reasons:

- Operational efficiency: protocols streamline the search process by clearly defining roles, search strategy adapted to the specific scenario and moment and all types of needs. This ensures that available human and dog teams, material, other resources (dogs, drones) are used effectively, and most urgent actions are carried out promptly: initially, delimiting infected areas and screening hotspots.
- Resource optimization: wild boar search protocols help prioritize search efforts in high-risk areas, such as known or suspected ASF-infected zones. Targeted sampling may identify high-risk zones (e.g., wild boar congregation areas, borders, habitat type, proximity to water sources) to focus efforts. This targeted approach avoids duplication of

effort and ensures that resources are used efficiently. For example, the use of GIS-based risk maps to guide search teams to high-risk areas.

- **Standardization and data reliability:** a well-defined protocol ensures that all search teams follow standardised procedures. This consistency is essential for comparing and analysing data across different areas and time periods (e.g., to evaluate different phases of the outbreak) or by different teams and methods. It also minimizes variability caused by individual differences in search techniques.
- **Statistical analysis:** consistent data collection is essential for robust statistical analysis, which is crucial for identifying trends and patterns in the recorded data.
- **Data integration:** protocols facilitate the integration of data from multiple sources, enabling comprehensive environmental assessments.
- **Biosafety and risk mitigation:** carcass searches can expose personnel to pathogens, in this case, as potential disseminators of ASF virus. Protocols must include proper biosecure measures from carcass detection to the end of search operations (before leaving the area).
- **Legal and regulatory compliance:** all activities must adhere to national and international regulations. Protocols ensure that these requirements are met and that the collected information is legally admissible.
- **Data integration for subsequent analysis begins in the field.** Standardised data collection on carcass search methods, effort and results is crucial for effective analysis and interpretation of data. This allows data to be integrated into broader databases and facilitates the traceability of wild boar search strategy results.
- **Facility of transference and public and stakeholder trust:** transparent, unified and science-based protocols enhance trust among stakeholders such as veterinarians, farmers and hunters. This trust is vital for effective ASF control and management. Good practice includes publishing/sharing wild boar carcass search results to build confidence.

3.1. Planning for searching wild boar carcasses

In order to be ready for an immediate and coordinated response to ASF, the preparedness of European countries that are currently free from ASF, either nationwide or in certain regions, must include effective collaboration between veterinary services, wildlife management authorities, hunters, and other relevant agencies. To this end, some countries have established interagency task forces to oversee ASF preparedness and response efforts. Comprehensive ASF contingency plans must outline the steps to be taken in the event of an outbreak, including measures for containing and eliminating the disease. These plans should also include simulation exercises to test their effectiveness and identify any gaps or areas for improvement.

The effective planning of wild boar carcass search operation would involve several key steps:

3.1.1 BEFORE: plan the search

– Defining objectives and scope

- The final objective is to detect and remove ASF-infected carcasses in order to prevent the spread of the disease, as well as to define the infected zones and surrounding areas for the search.
- Clearly define the geographical area of the search to include infected zones and surrounding areas in focal outbreaks, as well as large areas affected by the disease.

- For actions to be feasible and affordable, objectives must match the available collaborative framework, resources and methodologies. Even if they are not currently required, all logistical resources for potential emergencies must be anticipated and securely maintained. The magnitude and spatial spread of the disease in wild boar populations from the time of the virus's introduction until action is taken will impact the possibility of containment (e.g., Italy) or rapid elimination (e.g., Belgium, the Czech Republic and Sweden).
 - Once ASF is evidenced, the subsequent decision-making process will greatly contribute to determining what objectives are feasible and the final proceedings and outcomes (prompt elimination or spread and endemicity of infection).
 - The epidemiological situation (including the time since ASF introduction and present spread, the season, the habitat, the wild boar population density ...).
 - The applied methods and strategies.
 - All kinds of efforts that are required for that.
 - The availability of resources.
 - Team composition: describe the roles and responsibilities of each team member, such as field biologists, veterinarians, hunters, trained dogs and their handlers. These may include specific tasks such as leading the search, collecting samples, recording data and ensuring that biosecurity measures are followed. Clearly defining roles and responsibilities is essential to ensure that all team members understand their tasks and can work together effectively.
- **Making the established collaborative framework fully operative**
- Wild boar carcass searches require the involvement of various stakeholders, including veterinary services, forestry departments, hunting organisations and local communities.
 - Clear communication channels and coordination mechanisms, as well as a clear definition of responsibilities assigned to individuals and institutions, are crucial for efficient operations. For example, Belgium included administrative staff, forest rangers and military personnel in their teams, and set up a communication platform and a National Taskforce for ASF. Planning and conducting simulations are valuable exercises for evaluating coordination effectiveness.
 - The communication and coordination aspects identified must be practised by all stakeholders at all levels. Evaluating training outcomes plays a crucial role in enhancing operational capability.
- **Resource allocation and team preparation**
- Search teams must be adequately trained in carcass detection, biosecurity measures and data recording. This may include regular training sessions, workshops and practical exercises, ensuring all team members are familiar with and can carry out the procedures effectively. Training is essential to ensure that team members have the necessary skills and knowledge to perform their duties effectively and safely. All personnel must undergo training.
 - Basic ASF epidemiology and transmission
 - Protocol on carcass detection and identification
 - Biosecurity protocols and PPE use
 - Safe carcass handling and sampling techniques
 - Data recording and reporting procedures
 - Navigation tools (i.e., apps) and GPS for recording specific locations

- Necessary equipment, including GPS devices, PPE, and communication tools, which should be readily available:
 - GPS devices for accurate location recording
 - Maps of the search area
 - Disinfectants effective against ASFV (e.g., potassium peroxymonosulfate) for equipment and surface decontamination. Note that the use of the different disinfectants might be regulated by law.
 - To ensure effective documentation and data collection during wild boar carcass searches, the following tools are recommended:
 - Documentation Tools: waterproof notebooks and pens for taking notes in all weather conditions;
 - Imaging devices: digital cameras or mobile devices for capturing photographic evidence;
 - Navigation and tracking: GPS devices to accurately record locations;
 - Data recording: field data sheets or mobile applications designed for logging observations efficiently.
 - Signalling tape
- **Defining wild boar carcass search strategy**
 - Describe the search patterns (e.g., grid searches or transect lines) and methods (e.g., visual searches or the use of detection dogs or drones). This could involve guidelines for selecting search areas, optimising search patterns and combining different methods to enhance efficiency. Search strategies should be systematic and thorough, and adapted to the geographical area and specific epidemiological situation of the search. Initially, the search for wild boar carcasses will include presumably infected zones and surrounding areas. The results of these initial investigations into the scale, spread and chronology of ASF introduction should then inform subsequent actions.
 - From the first known cases, the infected zone must be searched for wild boar carcasses. Different strategies can be employed, either working from the centre outwards or vice versa, depending on the situation. All carcasses found must be registered, removed and disposed of safely. This should be complemented by surveying the riskiest hotspots in the surrounding area. Confirmation of new cases will determine subsequent areas to be surveyed.
 - Cooperate with local stakeholders, such as hunters, farmers and foresters, to share in-depth knowledge of the area and determine the main hotspots for searching for wild boar carcasses, particularly in remote sites, and facilitate prompt access to them. Good communication is essential for surveying the area for dead wild boar. Stakeholders such as hunters and the forestry/agriculture office can provide additional key contacts (e.g. local private rangers and hunters) who can be asked for evidence of dead wild boar in the area. The public can also report sightings of carcasses.
 - Once the infected zone has been delineated, search activities will focus on the infected area and its surroundings.
 - Priority areas for searching for wild boar carcasses, as well as the natural characteristics of the habitat (e.g. the distribution and abundance of forests) and the available information (e.g. the first cases versus already-delimited infected areas), may determine the shape, size and strategies of the searches. For example, this could involve using systematic spatial grids, habitat-driven methods, or first conducting a broad inspection of risky sites (which are favourable as deathbeds) through cost-effective surveillance or systematic combing. Depending on the size of the area, utilise methods such as grid

searches, transect lines and targeted searches in high-risk habitats, which are often forested areas. The choice between habitat-based and grid-based search strategies can significantly impact efficiency.

- Habitat-based strategies can be more efficient in targeted areas with known wild boar activity. These strategies prioritise searching areas where wild boar carcasses are most likely to be found, based on local, ecological and behavioural knowledge. Features usually considered for a habitat-based strategy include the presence of forests, proximity to water sources, forest types, terrain and areas with minimal human disturbance. This approach can save time and resources as searches are concentrated in areas where carcasses are most likely to be found, particularly in large or complex landscapes. However, this approach requires accurate habitat data and a good understanding of wild boar ecology, and it may miss carcasses located in less typical habitats.
- Grid-based strategies provide more comprehensive coverage and are useful in areas where habitat data is limited and local knowledge is lacking. While habitat-based strategies offer efficiency by targeting likely carcass locations, grid-based strategies prioritise thoroughness (Allepuz *et al.*, 2022; Rogoll *et al.*, 2024). A grid-based strategy involves a systematic search of a defined area by dividing it into a grid and searching each cell, thus ensuring comprehensive coverage of the search area. This systematic approach reduces the risk of missing carcasses in less obvious locations, but it can be very time-consuming and resource-intensive, especially in large areas and difficult terrain. It may also be inefficient as it involves searching areas with a low probability of finding carcasses and is less adaptable to varying terrain and habitat types. The size of the grids used to search for wild boar carcasses can vary depending on the specific objectives, method and landscape. Generally, grids are designed to ensure thorough coverage of the area while remaining manageable for search teams. For instance, grids ranging from 50 to 500 metres have been employed. The grid size can be adjusted based on factors such as the density of the wild boar population, the terrain, and the available resources.
- In many real-world scenarios, a combination of the two strategies is employed. For example, habitat-based strategies can be employed to identify high-priority areas, which are then thoroughly covered by grid-based searches. This balanced approach reduces the likelihood of missed carcasses. Based on our available data, habitat-based strategies can be efficient in targeted areas with known wild boar activity. Conversely, grid-based strategies provide comprehensive coverage and are useful in areas where habitat data is limited. Therefore, the choice between habitat-based and grid-based strategies should depend on the specific goals, the local situation and the available resources.
- Search frequency and timing: Search frequency should be increased in high-risk areas or following ASF outbreaks. It is advisable to consider seasonal factors and environmental conditions that may affect carcass visibility and decomposition rates.

– Define methodologies

Combining different methods, such as combing by teams of beaters, drones and canine units, can further enhance the efficiency of searching for wild boar carcasses. The main advantages and limitations of the applicable search techniques are summarised in Table 1.

Table 1. The main advantages and limitations of the techniques that can be used to search for wild boar carcasses.

Technique	Description	Advantages	Disadvantages	Applicability
Ground surveys: systematic searches by teams on foot	Teams systematically screening designated areas to locate and mark the carcasses (their location), may include dogs not necessarily trained on purpose.	Relatively high detection ratio, if n° of operators are sufficient, well trained and with good coordination, can be targeted to high-risk areas, allows for sample collection and on-site investigation.	Labour-intensive and time-consuming, limited coverage area, can be hampered by difficult terrain and weather conditions.	<p>Areas with known or suspected infection, outbreak areas with high wild boar density, surveillance in specific zones (e.g., near farms).</p> <p>Number of beaters and between-distance can be adapted. An integrated approach may enhance the efficiency and coverage of surveillance efforts, especially in areas that are difficult to access.</p> <p>Ground survey teams may work in conjunction with other surveillance tools, such as drones equipped with thermal imaging cameras and carcass detection dogs to enhance the efficiency of searches in dense forest areas.</p>
Ground surveys: patrolling known/possible hotspots by vehicles	Surveying known hotspots for wild boar activity and/or potential deathbed sites (risk-based surveillance), performed by teams with sound knowledge of the terrain, is a good approach to quickly identify carcasses over large areas.	Can be targeted to high-risk areas at site (if habitat allows), allows for sample collection and on-site investigation. Useful to initial delimitation of potential infected areas and early response (cover risky sites over large areas in a short time).	<p>Not useful for systematic surveying of a delimited area but complements and guides first actions.</p> <p>May not be feasible in many areas in Europe due to limited terrestrial accessibility.</p>	<p>By surveying, based on risk (e.g., water points) large areas with known or suspected infection, outbreak, it may help to delimit the infected zone over large areas, complementing further systematic searches.</p> <p>When wild boar carcasses are found, more systematic search activities (grids can be used) can be developed thereafter. Road/river transects, focus on linear features where carcasses accumulate.</p>
Trained dogs: use of specially trained dogs to locate carcasses by scent	The use of specially trained dogs to locate carcasses by scent. Systematic search patterns:	Probably highest detection ratio allows for sample collection and on-site investigation. Trained dogs are	Need of trained dogs (specific to detect wildlife carcasses, and namely, wild boar) and dogs'	Areas with known or suspected infection, outbreak areas with high wild boar density, but also surrounding areas can be surveyed. By considering

	implementing systematic search patterns, such as grid or transect searches, can help maximize the coverage and efficiency of the search. These patterns ensure that the area is covered thoroughly and that no sections are missed.	significantly faster due to their specialized training, experience and their ability to cover difficult habitats. Their ability to cover significant areas efficiently makes them an essential tool in disease surveillance and management efforts.	handlers. Dog-related biosecurity may be an issue. Need of permits may delay their rapid use. Their use may be limited by the availability of trained dogs and handlers. Heavy rain, extreme heat or specific wind regimes and air circulation dynamics in the search area can mask scents.	factors such as terrain, training, and environmental conditions, search teams can optimize the use of detection dogs to achieve the best possible results. The use of trained dogs may have up to three times higher efficiency in dense vegetation compared to searches conducted with human search chains.
Drones/ unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs): use of UAVs to cover large areas	Drones equipped with thermal imaging cameras.	Covers large areas quickly, can access difficult terrain, effective in open landscapes.	Expensive, requires skilled personnel and specialized equipment, can be affected by weather conditions (e.g., fog, rain).	Local and large-scale surveillance, surveillance in remote or inaccessible areas, rapid assessment of outbreak extent, use for detecting living wild boar in areas aiming for freedom of ASF, use for pre-harvest scans of field (in order to avoid spread of ASFV-infected wild boar).

- Estimating required effort

Table 2 presents general indicators of possible sampling efforts for searching wild boar carcasses according to methodology.

Table 2. Indicators of possible sampling effort for searching wild boar carcasses according to methodology.

Technique	Effort
Ground surveys: systematic searches by teams on foot	As indicative, the average number of people in teams participating in surveys (average per event) in most cases ranges from 5 to 10 people, the area screened per team and day also presented wide variation, with the majority of values around 100-200 hectares (ha) by team and day, whereas in terms of person per day, the screened surface ranged in most of the cases between 15-20 ha. Travel length most frequently ranging between 2-3 km, average speed mostly between 0.25 and 0.75 km/h, with some values above 1 km/h when dogs were used.

	<p>When present, the number of dog handlers per group typically was 1 or 2.</p> <p>As indicative, the practical implementation, for a 1 km² area (100 ha): 50 m grid: 20 transects × 1 km = 20 km of walking paths (needs 10 people x 50 m spacing).</p> <p>200 m grid: 5 transects × 1 km = 5 km of walking (needs 3 people).</p> <p>See guidance for spacing recommendations below*. Difficult terrain (e.g., dense vegetation, mountainous): smaller grids (50-100 m) due to topography.</p> <p>Tools for grid planning can be used (e.g., GPS apps) to mark search lines.</p>
<p>Ground surveys: patrolling known/possible hotspots by vehicles</p>	<p>Area covered per day is on the order of thousands of hectares a day but depends on accessibility by car. Cover is not systematic, as search is focused on potential hotspots for wild boar activity and/or potential deathbed sites (risk-based surveillance).</p> <p>Typical team of 2-3 people.</p>
<p>Trained dogs: use of specially trained dogs to locate carcasses by scent</p>	<p>The travel speed of dogs searching for wild boar carcasses can vary depending on several factors, including the breed, the dogs and their handlers training, the terrain, and the specific conditions of the search. Trained hunting dogs typically have an average search speed of around 5-8 km/h.</p> <p>Dogs without specialized training for carcass detection generally have a lower average search speed of about 4.5-5 km/h.</p> <p>Daily coverage: trained detection dogs can cover an area of approximately 10 to 20 ha per day. This coverage can vary depending on the intensity of the search, the weather conditions, and the specific site characteristics of the area being surveyed.</p> <p>Hourly coverage: on an hourly basis, trained dogs can cover around 1 to 2 hectares per hour. In addition to the limitations mentioned above, this rate can be influenced by factors such as terrain complexity and the presence of obstacles. See the guidance below for recommended spacing. **</p> <p>A typical team may consist of 2–3 people (one handler and one to two assistants/samplers).</p> <p>Considering the previously mentioned limitations related to terrain, weather, training, and other factors, dog-assisted searches can be organized using 200-meter grids, as dogs are able to detect carcasses up to 50 to 100 meters away from the transect line.</p>
<p>Drones/unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs): use of UAVs to cover large areas</p>	<p>Area covered per day of the order of several hundreds of hectares. However, the surface area covered by drones during wild boar carcass searches depends on drone type, flight parameters (the altitude at which it flies determines image resolution and area covered per flight and set of batteries), terrain, season, ambient</p>

	<p>temperature, and technology used (e.g., resolution of the thermal imaging camera).</p> <p>A typical drone team is composed of up to 4 people including 1 drone operator.</p> <p>Typically, drones can cover large areas quickly. For example, a drone flying at an altitude of 100 meters with a high-resolution thermal camera can cover several tens or few hundreds of ha a single flight.</p>
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* The optimal distance between beaters (searchers) during wild boar carcass searches for ASF control depends on the experience of the beaters and the visibility of the terrain. Thick vegetation and undergrowth reduce visibility, requiring closer spacing of beaters. If a very thorough search is required, closer spacing is essential. However, if the goal is to gain a quick overview, wider spacing may suffice. Experienced beaters may be able to cover more ground, allowing for wider spacing. We provide literature-derived spacing ranges in Table 3.

Table 3. Range of separations between beaters (searchers) during wild boar carcass searches.

Terrain type	Beater separation	Rationale
Dense forest (visibility <10m)	5-20 meters	Ensures overlapping visual coverage for small/decomposed carcasses
Open woodland (visibility 30-50 m)	20-40 meters	Balances effort with detection probability
Grassland/fields (visibility >100 m)	40-60 meters	Wide spacing possible with clear sightlines

With dogs, the beater separation can be up to 100 m spacing (dogs scent range covers gaps), without dogs: 50m maximum in forests.

To consider the relationship between spacing beaten beaters and search effort per time unit:

- 20 m spacing: increases the detection rate but is relatively slow (0.5 ha/person/hour)
- 50 m spacing: lower detection rate (2 ha/person/hour)
- 100 m spacing: probably <50% detection rate (4 ha/person/hour)

As shown in Figure 1 below, we present the comparative data from a separate report indicating the screened surface area (ha) per team and day, depending on the method used, which varies considerably. For example, in the case of dogs, the coverage depends on the size of the team (i.e. the number of dogs and dog handlers). It is likely that drones plus two ground teams could cover 50–100 ha/day (ENETWILD Consortium *et al.*, 2025).

Figure 1. Boxplot of the screened surface (ha) by a team and day, dependent on the method.

The optimal number of people for screening wild boar carcasses in ASF control areas depends on the type of terrain, vegetation, visibility, wild boar density and carcass density, as well as the search methodology.

Reported values regarding the areas searched do not provide insight into the effectiveness of carcass detection. No scientific study has yet been conducted to quantify search efficiency.

3.1.2 DURING: coordinate and carry out the search

– Coordinate search operations

During search operations, teams should implement the planned strategy while remaining flexible to adapt as the epidemiological situation evolves. The defined search areas must be systematically covered using the selected methods to ensure thoroughness and consistency. Close collaboration with stakeholders and local contacts is essential throughout the operations, as their knowledge and support can facilitate access and improve efficiency. Any new carcasses found should be reported promptly, allowing search priorities to be updated based on the latest findings.

– Data management and reporting systems

- Accurate and consistent data recording should include the following:
 - Date
 - GPS coordinates
 - Carcass decomposition condition
 - Environmental data (which may be considered when determining carcass PMI)
- Efficient data storage and reporting systems should be in place to ensure data integrity and accessibility.
- Ensure accurate and consistent recording of all relevant data. This includes standardised forms for recording data (see below), procedures for entering data into databases and guidelines for ensuring data accuracy and completeness. Accurate and consistent data recording is essential to ensure that the collected data is useful and can be analysed effectively.

– Ensuring biosecurity

- Strict biosecurity measures are essential to prevent the spread of disease during the search for and subsequent handling and disposal of wild boar carcasses. Carcass searches can expose personnel and equipment to pathogens such as ASFV, and these individuals

and items could then act as potential carriers and disseminators. Protocols must include proper biosecure behaviour when carcasses are found, as well as at the end of search operations (i.e. *in situ* before leaving the area).

- Protocols must include guidelines on personal safety and the safe handling of carcasses (unlike protocols on wild boar carcass searches, according to our review), including mandatory PPE and disinfection procedures.
- Boot baths must be used with ASF-approved disinfectants.
- Dogs must be washed down after completing searches or upon leaving the search area. Transport kennels and vehicles must also be cleaned using ASF-approved disinfectants.
-

3.1.3 Communicate and improve

– Post search data management

After the search operations, it is essential to ensure that all collected data are properly stored and remain accessible for future use. This information plays a critical role in supporting surveillance activities, guiding disease management decisions, and contributing to scientific research on ASF and wild boar populations.

– Continuous improvement and adaptation

- Wild boar carcass search protocols must be regularly reviewed and updated based on field experience and new scientific information. The results of carcass search surveys (in terms of design, method, effort and number of carcasses found) should be made available for further evaluation, comparison and improvement.
- Feedback mechanisms should be in place to allow for protocol adjustments and improvements, as well as facilitating mutual learning processes between different administrations and countries.

3.2 Wild boar carcass search data collection forms

Accurate and complete data sets are crucial for effective ASF surveillance, disease management and research, and form the basis for evidence-based decision making. We propose two forms to standardise the collection of data during wild boar carcass search operations: the first applies to the event and involves recording information describing the methods and effort applied; the second involves annotating wild boar carcasses found. These forms can easily be incorporated into apps on portable devices.

1. Form for the carcass search event

(Complete one form per search event)

General

- Search event ID:
- Search method:
- Date:
- Team/Personnel ID:
- Municipality:
- Hunting ground:
- Weather conditions:
 - Temperature (°C)

- Wind Speed (km/h or m/s)
- Precipitation (mm of rainfall or snowfall)
- Humidity (Percentage,%).
- Visibility (Meters or qualitative scale, e.g., clear, foggy, low visibility).
- Cloud Cover (influences lighting conditions for aerial imaging, Oktas or percentage)

Ground Surveys: systematic searches by teams on foot

- Start: (HH:MM)
- Ending: (HH:MM)
- Strategy (Y/N): 1. Grid _____ Indicate grid size (m) _____
2. Habitat-based _____ 3. Other _____
- Area screened (ha): _____
- Number of people:
- Team members (tasks): 1. _____ 2. _____ 3. _____ etc.
- Number of dogs used:
- Number of dogs handlers:
- Location Data
 - GPS Coordinates of the beater on the left-corner at start: Lat _____ Lon _____ (WGS84)
 - GPS Coordinates of the beater on the left-corner in the end: Lat _____ Lon _____ (WGS84)
 - Depict the screened area in a map (can be done in an app)
- Habitat Type:
 - Forest
 - Agricultural field
 - Grassland
 - Wetland
 - Other: _____

Ground Surveys: patrolling known/possible hotspots by vehicles

- Search event ID:
- Start: (HH:MM)
- Ending: (HH:MM)
- Area screened (the surface that encompasses the visited sites, ha): _____
- Number of people:
- Team members (tasks): 1. _____ 2. _____ 3. _____ etc.
- Location data (for every hot spot visited)

- GPS coordinates:
 - 1. Lat _____ Lon _____ (WGS84)
Site (habitat, use, e.g. water point, other) type:
 - 2. Lat _____ Lon _____ (WGS84)
Site type:
 - 3. Lat _____ Lon _____ (WGS84)
Site type:
 - 4. etc
- Use of dogs? _____

Trained dogs: use of specially trained dogs to locate carcasses by scent

- Search event ID:
- Start: (HH:MM)
- Ending: (HH:MM)
- Strategy (Y/N): 1. Grid _____ Indicate grid size (m) _____
2. Habitat-based _____ 3. Other _____
- Area screened (ha): _____
- N° people per team
- Team members (tasks): 1. _____ 2. _____ 3. _____ etc.
- N° dogs per team:
- Number of dogs handlers:
- Location data
 - GPS coordinates at start: Lat _____ Lon _____ (WGS84)
 - GPS coordinates in the end: Lat _____ Lon _____ (WGS84)
 - Depict the screened area in a map (can be done in an app)
- Habitat type:
 - Forested areas, Dense vegetation, under bushes, in thickets, or near tree roots.
 - Wetlands and marshes, consider wild boar carcasses can be partially submerged or hidden in reeds.
 - Agricultural fields, especially near corn, wheat, sunflower or other fields where boars forage. May be found at field edges or within crop rows.
 - Open grasslands or meadows, possible if the animal collapses while moving, easier to spot from drones or elevated observation points.
 - Near water sources, rivers, ponds, or artificial waterholes, carcasses may also be found along banks or in shallow water.
 - Human-modified landscapes, roadsides, abandoned buildings and structures providing shelter
 - Burrows or natural depression, as shallow beds or use natural hollows

- Other:

Drone-assisted wild boar carcass search

- Search event ID:
- Start: (HH:MM)
- Ending: (HH:MM)
- Strategy (Y/N): 1. Grid _____ Indicate grid size (m) _____
2. Habitat-based _____ 3. Other _____
- Automatic screening/manual search _____
- Area screened (ha): _____
- Location Data
 - GPS Coordinates:
 - Start. Lat _____ Lon _____ (WGS84)
 - Saved track of the screened area (Y/N)
- Drone operator: _____
- Drone model (for instance): [] DJI Mavic 3T [] Matrice 300 [] eBee X [] Other: _____
- Sensor type: [] RGB [] Thermal [] Multispectral [] LiDAR
- Flight parameters
 - Altitude: _____ m (AGL)
 - Ground Sampling Distance: _____ cm/pixel
 - Area Covered: _____ ha
- Weather conditions:
 - Temp: _____ °C
 - Cloud cover: [] Clear [] Partly Cloudy [] Overcast
 - Wind speed: _____ m/s
- Digital Integration Features
 - Automated fields:
 - GPS coordinates auto-captured from drone telemetry
 - Timestamp synchronization
 - Indicate overlap

2. Form for found wild boar carcasses

(Complete one form for every wild boar carcass or group (<10m) discovered)

General

- Search event ID:
- Search method:

I. Carcass Identification

- Date of Discovery: (DD/MM/YYYY), Time of Discovery: (HH:MM)
- Team/Personnel ID:
- Carcass ID (if tagged):
- Number of carcasses (in case of group, within 10 meters distance, consider as different observations if distanced more than 10 meters)

II. Location Data

- GPS Coordinates:
 - Latitude:
 - Longitude:
- Coordinates system: (e.g., WGS84)
- Location Description: (e.g., Forest, Field, Near Water Source)
- Distance to Nearest Landmark: (meters)

III. Carcass Condition (this is optional, can be incorporated to the form filled by staff collecting the samples and removing the carcass)

- Decomposition Stage: (Use a standardized scale)
 - 1 = Fresh
 - 2 = Early Decomposition
 - 3 = Moderate Decomposition
 - 4 = Advanced Decomposition
 - 5 = Skeletal/Remains Only

IV. Environmental Data

- Habitat Type: (Forest / Grassland / Wetland / Agricultural), more details can be provided:
 - Forested areas, Dense vegetation, under bushes, in thickets, or near tree roots.
 - Wetlands and marshes, consider wild boar carcasses can be partially submerged or hidden in reeds.
 - Agricultural fields, especially near corn, wheat, sunflower or other fields where boars forage. May be found at field edges or within crop rows.
 - Open grasslands or meadows, possible if the animal collapses while moving, easier to spot from drones or elevated observation points.

- Near water sources, rivers, ponds, or artificial waterholes, carcasses may also be found along banks or in shallow water.
- Human-modified landscapes, roadsides, abandoned buildings and structures providing shelter
- Burrows or natural depression, as shallow beds or use natural hollows
- Vegetation Cover: (Dense / Sparse / None)
- Terrain: (Flat / Hilly / Slope)

VII. Additional Information

- Observations: (e.g., Presence of scavengers, other wildlife)
- Deviations from Protocol: (If any, explain)
- Photographs Taken: (Yes / No)
 - Number of Photos:
 - Image File Name (for drones):

4. Guidance on wild boar carcass dating

The role of wild boar carcasses in the epidemiology of ASF is well documented. Often, due to a lack of more reliable data, the date on which the carcass is discovered is used as a proxy for the date of infection. However, our review suggests that this approach can lead to inaccurate estimates of infection timelines, particularly for older carcasses, resulting in flawed epidemiological assessments. The decomposition rate of wild boar carcasses varies significantly due to environmental factors such as temperature, humidity, sunlight exposure, and the activity of insects and vertebrate and invertebrate scavengers. To improve accuracy, we recommend implementing a standardised method for recording decomposition status alongside the date of discovery during ASF-free times. This would minimise discrepancies in infection dating, particularly in newly affected areas, as well as in high-risk zones where systematic carcass searches are conducted rather than relying on opportunistic findings. One practical solution would be to classify carcasses into five distinct categories according to their decomposition status (fresh, early decomposition, moderate decomposition, advanced decomposition or skeletal), and to include this classification in standardised data collection forms. This approach would enhance the reliability of ASF surveillance and outbreak analyses. Carcasses with an uncertain decomposition status, which are frequently encountered in early spring (particularly after cold winters), should be classified as 'date uncertain' to allow for their exclusion in subsequent epidemiological analyses.

Next, we summarize in Table 4 the main advantages and disadvantages, as well as the applicability for the different methods to date wild boar carcasses.

Table 4. Main advantages and limitations techniques that can be applied to date wild boar carcasses.

Type of technique	Technique	Description	Advantages	Limitations	Applicability to wild boar
Entomological	Forensic entomology	Studying insect activity on the carcass: insect species succession and age determination. While decomposition staging provides a general approximation, forensic entomology offers a more precise method by analysing insect colonization patterns	<p>Accurate in warmer months; can estimate PMI up to a few days or weeks.</p> <p>Entomology is particularly precise for dating fresh to moderately decomposed carcasses. Maggot age determination is more effective for estimating time since death when death occurred less than a month prior. Insect development is less affected by scavengers or weather than decomposition alone. Early-stage</p>	<p>Less reliable in colder months and advanced decomposition; requires specialist (entomological) knowledge and partly lab analysis. Insect succession normally applies when the carcass has been dead for a month or longer. Beyond ~14 days, insect succession becomes less predictable due to: competition between species, scavenger disruption (e.g., birds consuming larvae), carcass mummification/drying, which halts insect activity. For older carcasses, decomposition staging, or plant growth patterns may</p>	<p>High, especially in warmer seasons. Cross-referencing entomological data with decomposition stages reduces uncertainty. Recommendation: prioritize entomology for fresh carcasses (e.g., ASF "index cases" in new areas). Combine methods for carcasses >14 days old (entomology + decomposition + others)</p>

			carcasses: flies oviposit within hours of death, enabling PMI estimation even for fresh carcasses	complement entomology	
Physical	Decomposition stages	Observing physical changes in the carcass (e.g., fresh, bloated, decay). Provides a general timeline of decomposition stages to estimate time since death	Simple, quick initial assessment	Highly variable; subjective; limited accuracy	Low for precise estimates, useful for initial assessment
Physical	Partial Body Score (PBS)	Assigning scores to different body regions based on decomposition level (see Annex 3)	More objective than traditional staging; allows for 'mosaic' decomposition	Still somewhat subjective; requires training	Moderate, improves accuracy over traditional staging
Physical: microscopic	Microscopic analysis	Examining tissue changes under a microscope. Early cellular changes (e.g., autolysis, loss of cross-striations in muscle) can pinpoint death within hours to 3 days.	Can reveal details about decomposition processes	Requires specialized expensive equipment and expertise. Early stages only. Although microscopic analysis can outperform entomology in the first 48 hours, in terms of epidemiological assessment this is irrelevant	Moderate, depending on tissue preservation and at early stages. Microscopic techniques (histology, as well as microbiology, and biochemistry) can enhance early PMI estimation, but they are complementary to (not replacements for) entomology and decomposition staging
Chemical	Chemical analysis of tissues	Analysing changes in tissue composition (e.g., pH, volatile organic compounds)	Can provide insights into later stages	Requires lab analysis, expensive. May be affected by environmental factors	Complementary to (not replacements) for entomology and decomposition staging
Environmental	Carcass Decomposition Index (CDI) analysis / Soil analysis	Examining changes in soil chemistry and biology beneath the carcass	Can provide longer-term estimates; less affected by temperature	Requires soil sampling and analysis; may be influenced by environmental factors	Moderate, depending on soil conditions

Environmental	Accumulated Degree Days (ADD)	Calculating accumulated heat exposure based on temperature and time ("Heat units"). Helps refine the estimation of time since death by accounting for external influences	Accounts for temperature fluctuations; can be used with other methods	Requires accurate temperature data; influenced by other environmental factors; highly variable	Moderate, useful in conjunction with other techniques
Environmental, molecular	Microbiome	Microbiome-based PMI estimation leverages <i>post-mortem</i> microbial succession—the predictable changes in bacterial, fungal, and archaeal communities as a carcass decomposes. After death, the body's microbiome shifts from host-dominated (e.g., gut bacteria) to environmentally driven decomposers (e.g., Clostridium, Proteobacteria). By tracking these changes, researchers can estimate time since death. Key Techniques: 16S rRNA sequencing (bacteria/archaea), ITS sequencing (fungi), Metagenomics (whole-community analysis)	May work at early and late stages. Less affected by scavengers/environment. Potential for standardization (machine learning models)	Environmental variability: soil type, temperature, and humidity alter microbial succession, requiring region-specific calibration. Sample degradation risk: requires rapid freezing (−80°C) or preservatives (e.g., RNAlater) to prevent microbial overgrowth post-sampling. Cost and expertise: high-throughput sequencing and bioinformatics are expensive and lab-dependent. Wild boar-specific. Data gaps: most models use lab mice/pigs	Moderate, useful in conjunction with other techniques (metabolomics and entomology)
Molecular techniques	Genetics	Analysing DNA degradation or other molecular changes	Potentially very accurate; can be used in later stages, less affected by environment	Often expensive and time-consuming; requires specialized labs	Currently Low, but increasing potentials, more for research
Molecular techniques	Metabolomics	The study of small-molecule metabolites (e.g., amino acids, lipids, sugars). It tracks molecular decay signatures that change predictably after death	Less subjective, offers a highly sensitive, chemistry-driven approach to PMI estimation	Promising, but still under development. Requires lab analysis, expensive, needs specialized bioinformatics analysis	Potentially high, more for research. Field validation ongoing. Synergy with other methods: entomology, microbiome (microbial metabolite data can cross-validate PMI), decomposition

					staging (need to determine how molecular decay rates correlate with visual stages)
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In wild boar carcass surveillance, each dead animal found must be sampled and documented individually using a standardised dataset. To ensure accuracy, age determination should be based on tooth eruption. Assessing the stage of decomposition in the field can help to estimate the approximate date of death, particularly for individuals infected with ASF.

4.1. Wild boar carcass dating data collection

We present a general guidance plan, including a field protocol form for dating wild boar carcasses in the context of ASF control. The aim is to accurately determine the PMI of wild boar carcasses in order to improve ASF surveillance. The plan below ensures systematic data collection for further carcass dating, which supports ASF monitoring and helps to estimate infection timelines.

Preparation before fieldwork

Equipment needed:

- Personal Protective Equipment (PPE): disposable gloves, boot covers
- Sampling kit: swabs, scalpel, forceps, sample bags, containers, labels, cooler with ice
- Documentation tools: GPS device, camera, datasheet, waterproof pen, or digital devices
- Carcass assessment tools: decomposition scoring sheet, measuring tape
- Disinfection supplies: ASF approved disinfectants for people and equipment)
- Safety considerations: follow biosecurity protocols to prevent ASF spread (disinfect equipment, avoid cross-contamination)
- Means to record GPS coordinates and mark carcass location for follow-up

Carcass discovery and initial assessment

- Step 1: Locate and document. Record:
 - GPS coordinates
 - Date and time of discovery
 - Age class: age determination should be based on teeth eruption for accuracy
 - Habitat type (forest, field, water proximity)
 - Weather conditions (temperature, humidity, recent rainfall)
- Step 2: Photograph the carcass
 - Take multiple angles (surrounding, whole body, head, limbs, visible lesions, teeth – molars-, insects present, especially around mouth and anus)
 - Include a scale (e.g., ruler or glove for size reference)

Post-mortem decomposition assessment

Use a standardized decomposition scoring system (e.g., 5-stage scale):

Stage	Characteristics	Estimated timeframe PMI, only indicative in moderate climate, but other factors may be relevant
1 (Fresh)	No bloating, eyes clear, rigor mortis may be present	<24–48 hours
2 (Bloat)	Gaseous distension, tongue protruding, skin discoloration	Few days to few weeks
3 (Active decay)	Skin rupture, strong odour, maggot activity	Few weeks
4 (Advanced decay)	Reduced maggot mass, exposed bones, drying tissue	Few weeks to few months
5 (Skeletal)	Mostly bones, dried remnants, no soft tissue	Normally months (maybe >1 year)

Note that the estimated PMI requires experimental studies being regionally performed and over different seasons by enough carcasses deployed under natural conditions (in moderate climate), only indicative.

Additional indicators:

- Insect activity: presence of eggs, larvae (maggots), pupae
- Scavenging: bite marks, missing body parts (indicates predator/scavenger interference)
- Vegetation growth: grass/plants growing under carcass (longer TSD)
- Season: in winter slower decay as in summer

Collect information on environmental factors affecting decomposition

- Temperature: use a thermometer to record ambient and carcass core temperature (if fresh)
- Humidity and rainfall: accelerates decomposition
- Sun exposure: direct sunlight speeds up decay vs. shaded areas

Carcass disposal

- As required by regulations

4.2 Wild boar carcass dating collection form

Next, we present a structured field data collection form for estimating PMI in wild boar carcasses. This form can easily be incorporated into portable devices as an app, ensuring systematic data collection for PMI estimation in wild boar carcasses while accounting for environmental factors, decomposition stages and key indicators.

Field data collection form for PMI estimation in wild boar carcasses

See Probst *et al.* 2020, Annex 1.

(Complete one form per carcass found, it can be embedded in the above presented for wild boar carcass search)

General

- Search event ID:
- Search method:
- Observer name: _____
- Organization: _____
- Contact info: _____

1. Carcass discovery and initial assessment

I. Carcass identification

- Date of discovery: (DD/MM/YYYY), time of discovery: (HH:MM)
- Team/Personnel ID:
- Carcass ID (if tagged):
- Number of carcasses around (indicate the radius, m)
- Age class

II. Location data

- GPS coordinates:
 - Latitude:
 - Longitude:
- Coordinate format: (e.g., WGS84)
- Location description: (e.g., Forest, Field, Near Water Source)
- Distance to nearest landmark: (meters)

III. Habitat type:

- Forested areas, Dense vegetation, under bushes, in thickets, or near tree roots.
- Wetlands and marshes, consider wild boar carcasses can be partially submerged or hidden in reeds.
- Agricultural fields, especially near corn, wheat, sunflower or other fields where boars forage. May be found at field edges or within crop rows.
- Open grasslands or meadows, possible if the animal collapses while moving, easier to spot from drones or elevated observation points.
- Near water sources, rivers, ponds, or artificial waterholes, carcasses may also be found along banks or in shallow water. (specify distance: _____ m)
- Human-modified landscapes, roadsides, abandoned buildings and structures providing shelter
- Other (describe: _____)

IV. Weather conditions:

- Temperature: _____ °C
- Humidity: _____ %
- Recent rainfall (last 3 days): [] Yes [] No (if yes, amount: _____ mm)

V. Photographic documentation

- Photos taken? Yes No
- Angle captured:
- Surrounding
- Whole body
- Head (including teeth/molars)
- Limbs
- Visible lesions
- Scale included (ruler/glove for reference)
- Teeth
- Insects on carcass

2. Post-mortem decomposition assessment

Decomposition stage (select one) (see annex 2).

Stage	Characteristics	Estimated PMI (moderate climate)
<input type="checkbox"/> 1 (Fresh)	No bloating, clear eyes, rigor mortis possible	<24-48 hours
<input type="checkbox"/> 2 (Bloat)	Gaseous distension, tongue protruding, discoloration	Few days-few weeks
<input type="checkbox"/> 3 (Active decay)	Skin rupture, strong odour, maggot activity	Few weeks
<input type="checkbox"/> 4 (Advanced decay)	Reduced maggots, exposed bones, drying tissue	Few weeks-months
<input type="checkbox"/> 5 (Skeletal)	Mostly bones, dried remnants	Months->1 year

Additional indicators

- Insect activity:
 - Eggs present
 - Larvae (maggots) – stage: _____ (if known)
 - Pupae
- Scavenging evidence:
 - Bite marks
 - Missing body parts (specify: _____)
- Vegetation growth under carcass:
 - None
 - Slight growth
 - Significant overgrowth

3. Environmental factors affecting decomposition

- Ambient temperature: _____°C
- Carcass core temperature (if fresh): _____°C
- Humidity at site: _____%
- Sun exposure:
 - Full sun
 - Partial shade
 - Full shade

- Soil type: Dry Moist Muddy Other (_____)

4. Age estimation (based on teeth eruption)

- Juvenile/piglet (no permanent incisors)
- Subadult/yearling (2nd molar is visible, 1st incisor is permanent)
- Adult (full dentition)
- Teeth photos taken? Yes No
- 3 molar present Yes No

5. Additional Notes

Notes:

Decomposition rates vary with climate, season, surrounding vegetation, insect activity, and scavenger activity. PMI estimates are indicative and should be validated with regional experimental data. Further lab analyses may complement field data.

5 Conclusions

In conclusion, the recommendations presented in this report are the result of a comprehensive review of the available knowledge on wild boar carcass search and dating, combining evidence from the scientific literature, grey sources, and the practical experience of field professionals. Insights gathered through direct interviews with officials actively engaged in carcass detection and dating have been essential to complement the literature review and ensure that the proposed guidance reflects real-world challenges and solutions.

By integrating these diverse sources of information, the report offers practical and evidence-based recommendations aimed at improving the systematic detection and dating of wild boar carcasses for ASF surveillance and control. The proposed strategies and tools provide a harmonized approach to optimize field operations, enhance biosecurity, and standardize data collection.

Their implementation will strengthen the ability to estimate the timing of ASF introduction, improve outbreak response, and support coordinated disease management efforts across affected and at-risk areas. Regular application, transparent reporting, and continuous refinement of these practices—grounded in both science and field experience—will contribute to more effective ASF preparedness and control across Europe.

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